

The Art of Subperiosteal Tunneling - VISTA Technique in the Smile Zone: A Case Report

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Abstract

Gingival recession in the anterior esthetic zone presents both functional and cosmetic challenges. Traditional root coverage procedures often involve multiple incisions and limited predictability. The Vestibular Incision Subperiosteal Tunnel Access (VISTA) technique offers a minimally invasive alternative that enhances graft stability and esthetic outcomes. This study explores the effectiveness of the VISTA technique combined with Platelet-Rich Fibrin (PRF) membrane for the treatment of Cairo's RT1 multiple gingival recession. VISTA, a minimally invasive approach, uses a single vestibular incision to create a subperiosteal tunnel, allowing precise placement of PRF membranes. PRF, derived from the patient's own blood which used to enhance healing by promoting tissue regeneration. Clinical outcomes showed significant root coverage, increased gingival thickness, and improved keratinized tissue width. Patients experienced minimal discomfort and high esthetic satisfaction. The combination of VISTA and PRF offers a biologically driven, patient friendly solution for managing recession defects in the esthetic zone with predictable and favorable results.

Introduction

Gingival Recession is defined as the displacement of marginal gingiva apical to the cemento-enamel junction (CEJ).¹ It is characterized by the apical displacement of the gingival margin, exposing the root surface due to trauma, inflammation, or anatomical predisposition.² The prevalence of gingival recession tends to increase with age and is influenced by various local and systemic factors such as aggressive brushing, periodontal disease, malocclusion, frenal attachments, insufficient keratinized tissue, and iatrogenic issues like restorative overhangs.³ Indications for surgical intervention include esthetic concerns, defect progression, hypersensitivity, and hygiene challenges.⁴ Though often asymptomatic, it can impair both function and esthetics, affecting patient comfort and oral hygiene.^{4,5} This case report presents a minimally invasive technique Vestibular Incision Subperiosteal Tunnel Access (VISTA) introduced by Dr. Homa Zadeh in 2011 involving a single incision at the maxillary frenum and subperiosteal tunneling to facilitate coronal repositioning of the gingiva.⁶

The purpose of this case report is to evaluate clinically, the efficacy of the novel and minimally invasive VISTA in combination with PRF in the treatment of gingival recession defects.

Case Report

A 52 years old male patient reported to the Department of Periodontics, Institute of Dental studies & Technologies, Modinagar with a chief complaint of poor esthetics and hypersensitivity in upper front tooth region due to exposed root surfaces. To treat Cairo's RT1 maxillary anterior gingival recession, VISTA technique combines with PRF membrane was planned for root coverage.⁷ At his initial visit, thorough scaling and root planing was performed, patient instructed to maintain the oral hygiene and recalled after 2-weeks.

Surgical Procedure

In the VISTA approach, a vestibular access incision was made using no.15 BP blade, in the midline of the maxillary frenum, which provide access to the entire anterior maxilla. Subperiosteal tunnel was created by passing the incision through the periosteum and inserting a periosteal elevator between the periosteum and bone through the vestibular access incision. To mobilize gingival margins and facilitate coronal repositioning, the tunnel was extended at least one or two teeth beyond the teeth requiring root coverage. In order to achieve a low tension coronal repositioning of

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the gingiva, the tunnel was sufficiently elevated beyond the mucogingival junction as well as through the gingival sulci of the teeth being augmented. Subperiosteal tunnel extension was carried out interproximally under each papilla without making any surface incisions.⁶

Cairo's RTI recession defects at Maxillary left and right central Incisors respectively.

Following a Midline Frenum incision, a subperiosteal tunnel was created extending through the gingival sulci of the central incisors and beyond the mucogingival junction to allow for tension-free coronal repositioning of the gingival margins.

Freshly prepared platelet rich fibrin (PRF) membrane was trimmed to fit the dimensions of recipient site and the width was adjusted to extend at least 3-4 mm beyond the bony dehiscence's overlying the root surfaces.⁸ The PRF membrane was carefully inserted into the subperiosteal tunnel and repositioned below the gingival margin of each tooth. The membrane and mucogingival complex were then advanced coronally and stabilized in the new position with a coronally anchored suturing technique.⁹ Direct interrupted sutures at approximately 2-3 mm apical to the gingival margin of each tooth were placed using 3-0 silk suture.¹⁰ Sutures were tied, and the knots positioned at the mid coronal point of each tooth and stabilized by placing composite stops. Periodontal dressing was placed to cover the surgical site. Patient was prescribed analgesics for pain and 0.2% solution of CHX rinse 3 times a day for 14 days. Suture removal was done after 14 days.¹⁰

Following placement of PRF membrane within the subperiosteal tunnel.

The Midline incision was approximated and sutured primarily with multiple 5-0 ETHICON sutures. Initially, gingival margins were positioned coronally and anchored to teeth by placing composite stops.

After 10 days of follow-up.

After 3 months of follow-up, complete root coverage was observed at all six treated teeth, along with sustained gains in keratinized gingiva, linear root coverage, and clinical attachment levels.

Discussion

Gingival recession, particularly in the anterior esthetic zone, presents complex challenges for clinicians, including restoring the protective architecture of the periodontium, achieving esthetic harmony, and ideally regenerating lost periodontal structures i.e gingiva, cementum, periodontal ligament, and supporting alveolar bone.¹⁰ These challenges are amplified when multiple contiguous recession defects are present, as limited donor tissue and increased morbidity complicate treatment. In addition, the need for optimizing esthetic results through simultaneous treatment of contiguous defects tends to further challenge therapeutic success.¹¹ The Vestibular Incision Subperiosteal Tunnel Access (VISTA) technique offers a minimally invasive solution by allowing broad access through a single vestibular incision, typically placed within the maxillary frenum. This technique avoids trauma to the gingiva adjacent to the recession sites and preserves interdental papilla, enabling tension free coronal advancement of the gingival margin.⁶

When combined with Platelet-Rich Fibrin (PRF) membrane a second generation autologous biomaterial rich in growth factors the regenerative potential of the procedure is significantly enhanced.⁸ PRF's 3D fibrin matrix supports angiogenesis, boosts immunity, promotes osteoblastic differentiation, and guides wound

healing, affords a number of unique advantages to the successful treatment of multiple recession defects.¹¹ In the VISTA technique, access is broader and is made in the vestibule, where a single vestibular incision can provide access to an entire region, including visual access to the underlying alveolar bone and root dehiscences.⁶ The remote incision reduces the possibility of traumatizing the gingiva of the teeth being treated.⁸ Critical to the success of VISTA is a careful subperiosteal dissection that reduces the tension of the gingival margin during coronal advancement while at the same time maintaining the anatomical integrity of the interdental papillae by avoiding papillary resection.⁹ The VISTA approach overcomes some of the shortcomings of intrasulcular tunneling techniques used for periodontal root coverage.¹¹ Considerations of optimizing both blood supply and esthetics determine a vertically placed vestibular incision as superior alveolar arteries, branches of the internal maxillary artery, run in a superior inferior orientation. Therefore, a vertically oriented initial incision will less likely disrupt the blood supply than horizontally positioned incisions. Placement of the initial vertical incision and a tunnel entrance within the maxillary frenum results in little to no visible scarring, assisting in maximization of the esthetic outcome.⁶

Ethicon silk sutures are then secured to the facial aspect of each tooth, effectively preventing apical relapse of the gingival margin during the initial stages of healing but compensating for some degree of apical migration during the healing period.¹⁴ One of the major obstacles to regenerative healing is micromotion, which promotes formation of scar tissue.⁸ The rigid fixation of gingival margins introduced with the present coronally anchored suturing technique minimizes micromotion of the regenerative site. Reduction of micromotion has proven to be a major advantage of the present technique over conventional methods, where the gingival margin may be subject to displacement during facial movements.⁸ The combination of VISTA and PRF consigning both biological and esthetic demands, offering predictable root coverage, improved gingival biotype, and minimal postoperative morbidity. It shows a significant advancement in periodontal plastic surgery, particularly in the maxillary anterior region where esthetic outcomes are critical.

Conclusion

Based on the result, we can conclude that PRF membrane combined with the VISTA technique in multiple gingival recession defects, enhances gingival biotype and successfully promotes the healing. VISTA has shown excellent outcomes in the anterior esthetic region, delivering reliable root coverage with improved esthetics and patient satisfaction. Its minimally invasive approach and low postoperative morbidity make it a significant advancement in periodontal surgical procedures.

However, more clinical studies with longer period of follow-up with larger no. of patients are needed for better assessment of the VISTA technique with PRF membrane for the treatment of gingival recession.

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